

Table 3

SNP	chr	Pos	EA/OA	SNP-exposure			SNP-outcome		
				beta	SE	p	beta	SE	p
rs10015974	4	184196254	G/A	0.012	0.002	5.10E-11	-0.021	0.06	0.725
rs10029732	4	48498679	G/A	0.009	0.001	3.00E-09	-0.05	0.05	0.321
rs10037512	5	88354675	C/T	-0.014	0.002	8.60E-21	0.111	0.051	0.028
rs10040909	5	134515420	A/G	0.015	0.002	1.40E-15	0.019	0.063	0.759
rs10055993	5	264296	C/A	0.021	0.002	2.30E-20	-0.099	0.088	0.261
rs10059884	5	32832474	A/C	-0.027	0.002	5.80E-71	0.015	0.051	0.761
rs10061757	5	56086805	C/G	0.013	0.002	4.90E-16	-0.037	0.052	0.476
rs10082476	10	124164654	G/A	-0.015	0.002	1.40E-18	0.039	0.074	0.595
rs10094151	8	78757511	G/A	0.01	0.002	5.30E-10	0.033	0.051	0.524
rs10103539	8	8988073	G/A	-0.012	0.002	1.00E-14	0.026	0.065	0.686
rs10105330	8	58136501	T/C	0.014	0.003	1.60E-08	-0.144	0.094	0.125
rs10109521	8	21829948	A/G	-0.014	0.002	2.70E-20	0.014	0.05	0.774
rs10131337	14	37144516	T/C	0.015	0.002	2.50E-18	0.002	0.058	0.977
rs10142814	14	54655130	A/T	-0.029	0.004	2.50E-16	0.01	0.117	0.932
rs10148406	14	37492514	C/T	-0.011	0.002	1.20E-12	-0.017	0.053	0.751
rs10165255	2	10199601	G/A	-0.014	0.002	1.90E-20	0.007	0.056	0.903
rs10200618	2	1746140	G/T	0.012	0.002	1.70E-11	-0.074	0.054	0.171
rs10200995	2	164448385	A/T	-0.012	0.002	1.20E-08	-0.035	0.062	0.572
rs10400773	14	54063328	T/C	-0.015	0.002	1.60E-16	-0.06	0.067	0.366
rs10401891	19	4962848	T/C	-0.018	0.002	2.00E-30	-0.064	0.057	0.261
rs1044299	1	176811873	T/C	0.021	0.002	5.90E-44	-0.083	0.05	0.102
rs10498672	6	7797840	G/C	0.027	0.002	6.60E-42	0.01	0.061	0.865
rs10520597	15	86170255	A/G	-0.01	0.002	8.50E-11	0.086	0.058	0.143
rs1078690	5	171213774	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.70E-16	-0.106	0.052	0.043
rs10796937	1	155017385	A/T	0.011	0.002	2.80E-12	-0.065	0.053	0.22
rs10814077	9	34188563	C/T	0.009	0.002	1.30E-08	-0.017	0.051	0.74
rs10822055	10	52752880	A/T	-0.015	0.002	7.90E-17	0.031	0.058	0.593
rs10832963	11	18664241	G/T	-0.015	0.002	1.40E-18	0.004	0.052	0.943
rs10859554	12	94084994	C/T	-0.024	0.002	4.20E-49	-0.013	0.054	0.806
rs10861879	12	108609634	A/G	0.019	0.002	7.90E-31	0.05	0.052	0.335
rs10874746	1	93323971	C/T	0.013	0.002	4.30E-17	0.004	0.052	0.941
rs10877033	12	58283731	C/T	-0.014	0.002	6.90E-21	-0.008	0.05	0.872
rs10878984	12	69828534	T/C	0.018	0.002	1.70E-30	0.081	0.052	0.12
rs10887756	10	89597650	A/T	-0.011	0.002	7.50E-10	0.126	0.056	0.025
rs10901216	9	133471891	A/G	-0.02	0.002	1.00E-36	0.119	0.051	0.018
rs10914505	1	32393578	T/G	0.02	0.002	1.70E-19	-0.062	0.072	0.389
rs10948	19	10754905	T/G	-0.016	0.002	2.60E-24	-0.069	0.056	0.218
rs10952751	7	140266083	T/C	0.013	0.002	1.10E-15	0.046	0.057	0.423
rs11006752	10	28160836	C/T	0.012	0.002	7.70E-13	-0.048	0.053	0.367
rs11007551	10	29675588	T/A	0.012	0.002	1.10E-08	-0.048	0.06	0.425
rs11031991	11	32817441	A/G	0.01	0.002	5.30E-11	-0.01	0.05	0.836
rs11039348	11	47728617	A/G	-0.02	0.002	9.40E-37	-0.051	0.054	0.349
rs11060406	12	123339117	T/C	-0.032	0.004	1.80E-15	0.049	0.116	0.676
rs11067228	12	115094260	G/A	0.011	0.002	2.20E-14	0.076	0.052	0.145
rs11070250	15	40372057	A/G	0.011	0.002	1.40E-11	-0.023	0.056	0.674
rs11071642	15	62229356	C/T	-0.016	0.002	2.90E-25	-0.031	0.05	0.534
rs11076856	16	4949815	C/T	-0.01	0.002	6.30E-11	0.099	0.051	0.054
rs1108141	16	88841065	G/T	-0.018	0.002	7.70E-25	-0.033	0.062	0.596
rs11098733	4	124968702	T/C	0.019	0.002	6.90E-28	0.041	0.059	0.485
rs11103398	9	139134474	C/T	0.017	0.002	7.00E-23	-0.007	0.055	0.901
rs11107120	12	93985482	C/T	0.049	0.002	#####	0.053	0.058	0.36
rs11133373	4	56215631	G/C	0.011	0.002	2.90E-12	0.063	0.053	0.234
rs111526587	17	7261660	C/T	0.026	0.004	2.30E-10	0.029	0.129	0.821
rs11198886	10	121098290	T/C	0.022	0.003	1.30E-17	0.032	0.097	0.737
rs11204260	10	48533189	A/T	0.012	0.002	1.40E-12	0.022	0.053	0.686
rs11205303	1	149906413	C/T	0.016	0.002	3.60E-25	-0.044	0.054	0.418
rs11243202	6	7719065	C/T	0.026	0.001	6.80E-70	-0.015	0.05	0.764
rs11253170	10	5464706	G/C	0.014	0.002	1.90E-18	0.058	0.054	0.286
rs113116582	2	172415947	C/T	-0.018	0.002	2.60E-24	-0.005	0.064	0.943
rs113476837	18	29898930	C/A	-0.026	0.004	2.90E-11	-0.436	0.169	0.01
rs113518501	16	88915855	C/T	-0.02	0.003	3.10E-10	-0.201	0.14	0.15

rs113790954	2	204984410	A/G	-0.029	0.005	4.70E-10	0.189	0.205	0.359
rs113896694	16	88296825	T/C	-0.02	0.002	1.30E-17	0.032	0.067	0.635
rs113953187	22	46400764	A/G	0.02	0.003	2.70E-10	-0.185	0.103	0.071
rs1142	7	104756326	T/C	0.01	0.002	3.30E-10	0.008	0.054	0.883
rs11431	14	55255673	T/C	0.012	0.002	1.20E-15	0.088	0.05	0.08
rs114599229	2	190331954	G/A	0.04	0.005	1.80E-15	0.063	0.15	0.676
rs11555134	7	50659193	T/C	0.014	0.002	5.90E-15	-0.059	0.054	0.272
rs11588850	1	227927242	G/A	-0.026	0.002	4.00E-40	-0.047	0.063	0.46
rs11590658	1	224642854	C/T	-0.011	0.002	3.30E-09	0.022	0.06	0.706
rs116008080	16	67254841	A/G	-0.035	0.005	4.30E-12	-0.184	0.153	0.229
rs11615175	12	11898958	A/G	0.015	0.002	2.00E-21	-0.04	0.053	0.451
rs11635385	15	38662204	A/G	-0.016	0.002	1.50E-19	0.043	0.058	0.465
rs11638671	15	63795628	C/T	0.013	0.002	9.50E-16	0.093	0.051	0.07
rs11655860	17	79411662	A/G	0.011	0.002	8.20E-12	-0.019	0.052	0.717
rs116843977	19	34660410	G/A	0.035	0.005	9.60E-15	-0.485	0.273	0.075
rs11708067	3	123065778	G/A	-0.016	0.002	2.30E-19	0.093	0.067	0.161
rs11713042	3	41288004	C/T	0.014	0.002	1.50E-20	-0.054	0.051	0.284
rs1171615	10	61469090	T/C	-0.018	0.002	2.00E-23	0.044	0.069	0.52
rs11742177	5	37504165	T/G	0.019	0.002	3.40E-37	0.061	0.05	0.221
rs11743919	5	156754251	T/C	-0.016	0.002	1.60E-17	0.052	0.063	0.409
rs117542858	6	82570043	A/G	0.037	0.006	3.50E-10	-0.15	0.309	0.628
rs11764116	7	18800413	T/G	0.014	0.002	4.30E-14	0.079	0.059	0.176
rs11768221	7	156308895	A/G	0.009	0.002	2.00E-09	0.054	0.05	0.284
rs11778175	8	19267830	T/C	-0.012	0.002	8.20E-14	-0.035	0.053	0.513
rs11779459	8	123980551	T/C	0.013	0.002	1.30E-15	-0.034	0.055	0.541
rs11794152	9	23345347	G/A	0.009	0.002	1.40E-08	0.061	0.051	0.23
rs118115924	12	49379537	T/G	-0.053	0.007	3.40E-14	1.121	0.661	0.09
rs118173451	22	28356600	C/T	-0.075	0.006	5.60E-35	0.03	0.209	0.887
rs11840862	13	42956463	G/A	-0.013	0.002	8.80E-16	0.006	0.054	0.918
rs11954686	5	52787926	G/A	-0.011	0.002	2.10E-08	-0.013	0.066	0.843
rs11983105	7	121439019	G/A	-0.009	0.002	8.60E-10	0.056	0.05	0.266
rs12032733	1	204481209	A/G	0.009	0.002	1.10E-08	0.054	0.061	0.375
rs12088601	1	26445504	A/G	0.024	0.002	9.00E-35	0.054	0.069	0.437
rs12093819	1	26716797	T/C	0.013	0.002	1.70E-10	-0.098	0.07	0.158
rs12095997	1	51391845	T/C	0.026	0.003	7.30E-23	0.024	0.109	0.827
rs12129705	1	120191044	T/A	-0.017	0.002	3.20E-14	0.024	0.078	0.755
rs12130046	1	67444043	A/G	-0.015	0.002	1.40E-12	-0.068	0.06	0.262
rs12154695	7	115970622	T/G	-0.013	0.002	2.80E-16	0.007	0.058	0.904
rs12185775	20	20293769	C/G	-0.014	0.002	6.50E-09	0.011	0.073	0.877
rs12185993	3	188565410	A/T	0.011	0.002	4.40E-10	0.068	0.057	0.234
rs12200852	6	168887333	T/C	-0.016	0.002	1.70E-18	0.006	0.054	0.913
rs12213409	6	142610314	G/T	-0.015	0.002	7.70E-23	0.048	0.05	0.341
rs12222197	11	125825224	T/G	0.016	0.002	7.80E-26	-0.054	0.052	0.292
rs12296991	12	132643598	T/C	0.013	0.002	9.40E-10	-0.116	0.072	0.107
rs12339639	9	97786816	T/C	-0.024	0.003	3.30E-19	0.04	0.095	0.67
rs12347137	9	119122721	C/A	-0.033	0.002	1.30E-70	0.011	0.06	0.857
rs12348423	9	4740251	C/A	-0.014	0.002	5.50E-15	0.061	0.06	0.308
rs12408482	1	54112148	A/G	0.02	0.002	2.00E-31	0.062	0.061	0.311
rs12452505	17	63556402	G/C	-0.025	0.002	1.40E-31	0.08	0.083	0.335
rs12459155	19	4774475	G/C	-0.015	0.002	7.30E-11	0.002	0.08	0.98
rs12471240	2	233864627	C/G	-0.024	0.002	2.10E-34	-0.053	0.066	0.417
rs12477783	2	174841455	A/G	0.023	0.003	2.50E-15	-0.125	0.085	0.14
rs12584833	13	100393168	T/A	-0.011	0.002	1.50E-12	0.025	0.052	0.629
rs12620308	2	36769028	A/G	0.01	0.002	8.80E-11	-0.076	0.052	0.144
rs12635093	3	152150885	T/C	-0.012	0.002	1.60E-11	-0.02	0.066	0.759
rs12662365	6	80905389	A/T	-0.038	0.002	#####	-0.025	0.055	0.651
rs12694416	2	218289497	C/A	0.026	0.002	2.80E-64	-0.007	0.05	0.888
rs12700439	7	23472061	C/T	-0.015	0.002	1.60E-23	0.03	0.053	0.575
rs12711538	2	121747406	A/G	-0.01	0.002	8.00E-10	0.025	0.053	0.645
rs12751561	1	103763039	A/G	0.018	0.002	1.90E-15	-0.056	0.085	0.51
rs12881989	14	70425719	C/T	0.008	0.002	2.70E-08	0.055	0.052	0.285
rs12895262	14	54441319	T/A	0.018	0.003	2.80E-11	-0.074	0.117	0.53
rs12925127	16	24728185	A/G	0.012	0.002	1.80E-14	0.067	0.054	0.217
rs12982509	19	3412057	C/T	0.014	0.002	8.20E-15	-0.078	0.059	0.19

rs12985850	19	2155042	A/G	0.02	0.002	2.30E-37	0	0.053	0.994
rs12989676	2	199776050	G/A	0.013	0.002	1.70E-11	0.073	0.081	0.363
rs13030579	2	46717743	A/G	0.012	0.002	1.40E-14	-0.025	0.053	0.638
rs13037063	20	47525665	A/G	0.021	0.002	1.90E-32	0.058	0.061	0.344
rs13077145	3	194064366	C/G	0.01	0.002	4.30E-09	-0.021	0.057	0.709
rs13079205	3	135800693	G/A	-0.011	0.002	3.40E-10	0.105	0.062	0.089
rs13120807	4	175925138	A/G	0.009	0.002	3.40E-08	-0.066	0.055	0.227
rs13125694	4	145566848	T/C	0.041	0.002	#####	-0.08	0.05	0.113
rs13146714	4	146179152	C/T	-0.022	0.003	5.00E-11	-0.07	0.137	0.609
rs1317394	1	172208204	C/T	0.031	0.002	5.90E-66	-0.079	0.063	0.207
rs1317867	17	21276114	G/A	0.012	0.002	2.90E-14	-0.027	0.05	0.597
rs1319012	6	41852616	A/T	-0.038	0.003	6.90E-38	0.033	0.084	0.695
rs13195171	6	33558751	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.40E-11	0.034	0.06	0.574
rs13237676	7	95593062	A/C	0.012	0.002	1.10E-09	0.144	0.073	0.05
rs1327124	1	184014199	G/A	0.024	0.002	1.30E-52	0.002	0.051	0.968
rs1328369	13	93912990	T/C	-0.011	0.002	4.30E-14	-0.02	0.05	0.693
rs13316	14	93407301	A/C	0.009	0.002	1.60E-08	0.038	0.051	0.456
rs13318536	3	98679802	G/C	0.016	0.002	3.50E-13	-0.051	0.076	0.501
rs13386930	2	23871024	A/G	0.015	0.002	6.00E-12	0.059	0.065	0.358
rs1342131	1	82292250	C/T	0.01	0.002	2.10E-11	0.051	0.05	0.308
rs1346131	4	138280248	T/C	0.012	0.002	1.50E-16	0.018	0.05	0.714
rs1360504	1	56627905	A/G	0.015	0.002	8.60E-15	0.077	0.063	0.221
rs1373573	12	20533594	C/T	0.015	0.002	3.20E-20	0.062	0.058	0.282
rs1376264	7	37958289	A/G	0.012	0.002	1.50E-14	0.018	0.054	0.743
rs140228304	16	391363	A/G	-0.02	0.003	1.10E-11	-0.143	0.109	0.188
rs1415701	6	130345835	A/G	-0.028	0.002	2.10E-59	-0.031	0.058	0.591
rs1421002	3	169329676	C/T	-0.01	0.002	8.20E-12	-0.035	0.05	0.48
rs1431181	18	50779412	A/G	0.018	0.002	2.50E-30	-0.094	0.051	0.068
rs1433352	3	13838070	C/G	-0.012	0.002	3.20E-15	0.057	0.052	0.271
rs143384	20	34025756	G/A	0.062	0.002	#####	0.005	0.051	0.917
rs145216811	4	81591659	A/G	0.043	0.006	1.00E-14	0.206	0.34	0.545
rs145350287	12	120907309	A/T	-0.028	0.004	5.10E-13	0.054	0.132	0.683
rs146381464	3	51463177	A/C	0.065	0.005	6.20E-38	-0.134	0.205	0.513
rs146851424	13	50377910	C/A	0.074	0.005	9.20E-46	-0.296	0.188	0.114
rs147110934	19	55993436	T/G	-0.053	0.005	2.50E-27	0.32	0.333	0.337
rs1474043	18	12951738	A/G	-0.011	0.002	6.10E-12	0.055	0.05	0.274
rs147724226	10	79584060	T/C	-0.057	0.006	8.60E-21	-0.266	0.213	0.212
rs1490384	6	126851160	T/C	0.033	0.001	#####	0.033	0.05	0.512
rs150606467	2	1568378	A/G	0.028	0.004	5.50E-13	0.232	0.239	0.332
rs151102833	14	35226811	T/C	0.015	0.002	3.60E-09	0.096	0.067	0.155
rs151123887	20	34593288	A/G	-0.038	0.005	1.40E-12	-0.222	0.328	0.497
rs1527210	7	16275681	T/C	0.009	0.002	3.60E-10	0.004	0.05	0.94
rs1561819	18	2712629	G/A	-0.01	0.002	2.30E-11	-0.039	0.05	0.442
rs1566610	5	73066154	A/T	-0.012	0.002	1.20E-12	0.117	0.054	0.031
rs1592269	6	34183057	A/G	-0.056	0.003	1.80E-61	-0.01	0.156	0.949
rs1599473	8	120475358	T/G	-0.018	0.002	6.50E-24	-0.137	0.061	0.025
rs1623354	4	40160011	A/G	0.012	0.002	9.80E-11	-0.022	0.062	0.73
rs1662835	4	82172449	C/T	0.026	0.002	4.30E-59	-0.041	0.052	0.43
rs1667618	2	74347666	G/T	-0.009	0.002	1.10E-09	-0.067	0.052	0.198
rs16887945	4	13005264	C/T	0.034	0.006	5.40E-09	-0.197	0.184	0.286
rs16936387	9	113940924	A/G	-0.011	0.002	1.70E-13	-0.058	0.05	0.244
rs16941866	16	86725901	T/C	-0.014	0.002	5.40E-11	0.043	0.066	0.516
rs17110280	14	80569705	C/T	-0.01	0.002	1.10E-08	0.078	0.054	0.153
rs17141318	7	19481867	C/T	0.027	0.003	2.30E-26	0.004	0.085	0.961
rs17148514	11	85526399	T/C	-0.012	0.002	2.10E-12	0.144	0.067	0.031
rs17232373	1	234792421	G/T	0.016	0.002	2.00E-15	0.093	0.075	0.215
rs173335	5	138995064	C/T	0.028	0.003	1.30E-20	-0.084	0.142	0.556
rs17369123	1	172355841	T/C	0.019	0.002	4.30E-24	0.143	0.062	0.022
rs17384485	8	27560651	T/C	-0.009	0.002	1.50E-08	-0.035	0.051	0.491
rs17400325	2	178565913	C/T	0.048	0.004	1.90E-37	-0.237	0.178	0.183
rs17404047	20	32305781	T/A	-0.028	0.002	3.40E-60	0.007	0.06	0.906
rs17454077	4	87631532	G/A	0.025	0.004	7.20E-10	-0.333	0.249	0.181
rs17481050	12	24170904	T/C	0.021	0.002	6.90E-30	0.002	0.063	0.971
rs17647041	18	33097189	A/G	0.011	0.002	7.40E-09	-0.118	0.062	0.058

rs17725162	7	33472130	G/A	-0.009	0.002	1.10E-08	0.116	0.055	0.034
rs17743415	2	71562503	C/T	-0.021	0.002	1.50E-42	0.025	0.05	0.625
rs17800727	16	53481010	G/A	0.019	0.002	6.30E-32	0.014	0.057	0.81
rs17823744	5	78344976	G/A	0.013	0.002	6.10E-09	0.075	0.083	0.364
rs1791495	11	74265980	A/G	-0.016	0.002	5.90E-18	-0.079	0.061	0.192
rs1795170	3	112826662	A/G	0.01	0.002	9.00E-10	0.007	0.051	0.885
rs1814034	3	54998414	G/A	0.011	0.002	2.30E-12	-0.056	0.05	0.264
rs1823217	3	134380959	G/A	-0.009	0.002	2.80E-08	-0.041	0.055	0.456
rs183127319	4	106232969	C/A	-0.027	0.005	1.90E-09	-0.29	0.386	0.452
rs1853655	6	18524374	C/T	0.009	0.002	3.20E-08	0.023	0.058	0.694
rs186606513	2	97482001	A/G	-0.056	0.006	4.20E-19	0.067	0.145	0.646
rs1900016	10	69941134	T/C	0.022	0.002	1.50E-49	-0.048	0.05	0.342
rs1910466	3	147086268	C/T	-0.019	0.002	4.30E-35	0.037	0.05	0.458
rs1963689	6	127425630	C/T	0.014	0.002	4.30E-15	0.057	0.059	0.329
rs1971929	11	2773371	C/G	0.025	0.002	1.30E-31	-0.06	0.064	0.348
rs1978427	5	77430426	A/G	-0.024	0.002	2.00E-43	-0.069	0.065	0.29
rs1979923	5	168265891	C/T	-0.021	0.002	2.50E-34	-0.084	0.058	0.147
rs2005172	17	61996255	C/A	0.031	0.002	3.20E-84	0.021	0.051	0.677
rs2007022	20	3237674	A/C	0.015	0.002	9.40E-17	0.093	0.07	0.184
rs2008952	2	191583066	A/G	-0.009	0.002	2.70E-08	-0.018	0.051	0.73
rs2025866	6	85396512	A/G	-0.014	0.001	2.40E-21	0.009	0.05	0.86
rs2028106	2	85766282	G/C	-0.032	0.004	4.60E-14	0.023	0.21	0.912
rs2028918	2	149512886	C/T	-0.013	0.002	2.30E-09	-0.003	0.066	0.967
rs2075060	17	36925750	A/G	0.019	0.002	1.40E-34	0.022	0.05	0.669
rs2088483	4	106216367	C/T	-0.024	0.002	7.40E-55	0.059	0.052	0.254
rs2089035	2	219898076	T/C	-0.013	0.002	1.80E-08	0.208	0.078	0.008
rs2100361	7	134433635	G/A	-0.015	0.002	2.90E-23	-0.01	0.053	0.848
rs2119260	15	67011946	C/T	-0.023	0.002	1.40E-42	0.057	0.056	0.312
rs2140046	2	169706079	C/T	-0.016	0.002	4.70E-24	0.03	0.051	0.556
rs2194411	3	185548663	A/G	0.04	0.002	2.10E-70	0.019	0.073	0.798
rs222486	2	42649664	T/C	-0.02	0.002	1.40E-18	0.053	0.074	0.476
rs2225226	13	51127270	T/C	-0.036	0.002	7.50E-88	0.013	0.058	0.824
rs2231940	19	41944237	C/T	0.016	0.002	5.60E-25	-0.03	0.052	0.565
rs2240795	5	149589647	G/A	0.009	0.001	3.20E-09	-0.077	0.052	0.139
rs2256609	22	21925017	G/A	-0.017	0.002	1.70E-18	0.028	0.055	0.616
rs2270894	3	9975386	G/C	-0.026	0.002	7.40E-41	0.014	0.057	0.803
rs2295300	14	24805117	T/C	0.013	0.002	2.30E-15	0.01	0.056	0.858
rs2296316	14	65520246	C/T	-0.016	0.002	1.30E-26	-0.001	0.05	0.989
rs2296782	10	114723857	G/A	-0.01	0.002	2.50E-08	0.024	0.057	0.68
rs2309725	2	100338404	A/C	0.01	0.002	1.00E-11	-0.109	0.051	0.031
rs2445351	8	108375183	T/A	-0.012	0.002	4.30E-09	-0.031	0.077	0.684
rs2450992	12	48746675	C/T	0.015	0.002	6.70E-23	0.036	0.051	0.475
rs2451948	9	109518208	G/A	0.025	0.002	7.40E-33	0.113	0.076	0.134
rs246242	5	129059497	G/A	-0.033	0.003	3.60E-31	-0.038	0.08	0.629
rs2471548	7	46042442	C/T	0.021	0.002	6.10E-45	-0.064	0.05	0.201
rs2480711	1	2111376	G/A	0.011	0.002	2.30E-13	0.032	0.052	0.54
rs2513289	11	68419655	C/A	0.022	0.002	2.40E-26	-0.081	0.088	0.36
rs2523578	6	31328542	A/G	-0.034	0.002	4.70E-96	-0.001	0.065	0.982
rs2526639	7	19016165	A/G	0.013	0.002	5.10E-13	0.018	0.058	0.762
rs2545159	5	112159562	G/A	-0.015	0.002	2.70E-21	0.074	0.051	0.148
rs2573668	15	100541776	C/T	0.013	0.002	2.00E-17	-0.011	0.051	0.832
rs2610986	4	18037231	T/C	-0.017	0.002	9.00E-26	-0.047	0.053	0.378
rs2647116	1	219009835	A/G	-0.014	0.002	2.40E-19	-0.034	0.051	0.507
rs2648725	10	93015079	A/T	0.017	0.002	2.20E-19	0.022	0.066	0.742
rs2650965	20	6709838	G/A	-0.022	0.002	3.50E-42	0.049	0.054	0.362
rs2663110	15	99550565	G/C	-0.014	0.002	2.00E-14	-0.051	0.064	0.429
rs2679532	3	187622411	A/C	0.011	0.002	1.60E-09	0.018	0.054	0.747
rs26835	16	2237549	T/C	0.016	0.002	8.90E-26	0.045	0.051	0.372
rs2684780	15	99406879	C/G	0.014	0.002	2.60E-14	-0.014	0.055	0.801
rs2737218	8	116631278	C/T	-0.022	0.002	2.40E-32	-0.029	0.055	0.597
rs2744700	1	22498374	T/C	0.024	0.002	3.60E-57	-0.029	0.052	0.575
rs2808290	10	27900882	T/C	0.018	0.002	5.10E-32	0.02	0.051	0.696
rs2832019	21	30112207	G/A	-0.016	0.002	4.00E-13	-0.037	0.061	0.545
rs28409768	15	99193524	T/C	-0.052	0.004	3.20E-32	0.217	0.16	0.174

rs28507795	4	26019677	A/G	0.015	0.003	2.60E-09	0.139	0.085	0.1
rs28583508	15	100800049	T/G	-0.014	0.002	6.40E-19	0.073	0.056	0.194
rs28584580	15	89397827	G/A	-0.079	0.004	1.10E-73	-0.016	0.214	0.94
rs28610581	15	75812474	G/A	0.017	0.002	5.50E-24	0.008	0.062	0.896
rs28615587	9	136365146	G/T	0.011	0.002	7.30E-12	-0.144	0.057	0.012
rs2871960	3	141121814	C/A	0.046	0.002	#####	-0.101	0.05	0.044
rs2877763	17	54712328	A/G	0.026	0.003	2.10E-14	-0.016	0.113	0.884
rs2885697	1	41544279	T/G	-0.023	0.002	1.20E-47	0.034	0.053	0.516
rs28929474	14	94844947	T/C	0.072	0.005	1.00E-40	0.707	0.189	0
rs2894602	2	227249802	G/A	0.015	0.002	3.40E-16	-0.072	0.06	0.23
rs2907384	17	66576439	T/G	-0.01	0.002	2.00E-09	0.094	0.056	0.09
rs2922873	8	6398327	G/A	0.014	0.002	1.00E-10	-0.088	0.065	0.176
rs2936701	12	106648099	C/T	0.011	0.002	9.60E-12	-0.004	0.051	0.942
rs2944766	8	141558980	T/C	0.009	0.002	2.90E-10	-0.053	0.05	0.292
rs2954869	8	75846609	G/A	-0.013	0.002	1.30E-13	0.094	0.056	0.093
rs2980812	8	40050549	T/C	0.01	0.002	1.40E-08	-0.048	0.057	0.4
rs3006073	5	14958415	T/C	0.016	0.002	4.20E-14	0.016	0.071	0.817
rs3006926	1	243655452	G/A	0.014	0.002	4.40E-16	-0.042	0.058	0.465
rs30233	16	14400309	A/G	0.01	0.002	2.50E-11	0.037	0.051	0.472
rs310307	8	23651661	G/A	-0.015	0.002	1.70E-23	-0.013	0.05	0.802
rs310796	12	77453226	T/G	0.011	0.002	5.50E-11	-0.032	0.057	0.581
rs3110417	8	89476451	G/T	-0.01	0.002	2.10E-08	-0.007	0.058	0.906
rs31210	5	134361020	A/G	-0.018	0.002	3.90E-24	-0.001	0.058	0.981
rs3252	6	169616097	T/C	0.019	0.003	4.30E-08	-0.173	0.097	0.075
rs337606	4	38659263	T/G	-0.014	0.002	8.20E-13	-0.095	0.07	0.174
rs34060476	7	73037956	G/A	0.023	0.002	2.00E-26	-0.131	0.074	0.077
rs34162548	11	14556220	T/C	0.029	0.003	7.80E-18	-0.03	0.095	0.748
rs34350503	4	123827911	G/A	-0.012	0.002	1.10E-12	0.003	0.062	0.96
rs34454426	3	87346735	A/G	-0.02	0.003	4.60E-09	0.1	0.098	0.304
rs34517439	1	78450517	A/C	0.028	0.002	1.00E-34	0.051	0.075	0.501
rs34587452	4	1009900	C/G	-0.011	0.002	4.80E-10	-0.036	0.063	0.572
rs34678188	2	242605422	A/G	-0.009	0.002	1.70E-08	-0.009	0.053	0.861
rs34831515	19	17275777	T/C	-0.016	0.002	3.00E-18	-0.036	0.054	0.503
rs34919557	20	32510282	T/C	-0.016	0.003	4.00E-10	0.096	0.074	0.195
rs35065130	17	61826504	T/C	-0.019	0.002	3.30E-16	0.015	0.08	0.847
rs35231678	10	4985193	C/T	-0.033	0.002	1.80E-45	0.085	0.074	0.254
rs35307904	9	78511889	A/G	-0.023	0.002	3.60E-23	0.008	0.069	0.906
rs35344256	17	79934194	A/C	-0.021	0.002	4.20E-38	0.164	0.056	0.004
rs35364449	15	74278126	T/C	-0.021	0.002	1.30E-17	0.059	0.072	0.413
rs35399883	18	74204354	C/G	0.01	0.002	3.60E-10	0.009	0.053	0.872
rs35485741	1	151241909	C/G	-0.017	0.002	2.30E-13	-0.057	0.08	0.482
rs35506085	11	2165576	A/G	-0.028	0.002	2.80E-45	0.06	0.066	0.364
rs35548026	21	47552209	A/G	0.021	0.003	1.30E-15	0.208	0.09	0.02
rs35590487	14	105989599	T/C	0.011	0.002	1.10E-09	0.04	0.056	0.475
rs35990522	9	119274481	A/T	0.028	0.003	3.20E-23	0.223	0.149	0.135
rs369625	5	122560787	C/G	-0.01	0.002	1.60E-11	-0.022	0.051	0.663
rs3732858	3	43097765	A/G	-0.015	0.002	4.90E-14	0.03	0.065	0.643
rs3756668	5	67596088	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.60E-17	0.015	0.051	0.775
rs3756991	6	55620218	A/C	-0.02	0.002	1.10E-16	-0.018	0.065	0.788
rs3759819	15	72299982	C/T	0.038	0.005	5.80E-13	0.402	0.295	0.173
rs3762942	4	2233009	A/G	-0.022	0.003	4.00E-11	-0.052	0.137	0.706
rs3770865	2	36690109	A/G	-0.01	0.002	2.80E-08	0.074	0.06	0.215
rs3789280	9	118953372	A/T	0.01	0.002	3.40E-11	-0.049	0.051	0.339
rs3804664	3	145810408	A/G	0.013	0.002	5.40E-19	-0.017	0.051	0.741
rs3812277	7	135067234	C/T	0.015	0.002	2.70E-20	-0.051	0.052	0.325
rs3815305	2	242054403	A/G	0.015	0.003	6.00E-09	0.026	0.075	0.726
rs3815570	12	107390867	T/C	-0.011	0.002	3.10E-12	-0.064	0.05	0.201
rs3827187	21	38170479	G/A	-0.016	0.002	7.00E-24	-0.064	0.055	0.241
rs3849773	5	39437527	T/C	-0.012	0.002	4.90E-13	-0.003	0.051	0.953
rs387641	22	18292242	C/A	0.011	0.002	1.70E-10	0.002	0.054	0.971
rs4073154	3	129035485	G/A	0.024	0.002	1.50E-39	-0.013	0.067	0.851
rs4073717	5	170864021	T/G	-0.03	0.002	1.20E-56	0.04	0.064	0.531
rs41271299	6	19839415	T/C	0.058	0.003	3.80E-66	-0.168	0.199	0.397
rs41311445	22	42070374	C/A	-0.028	0.003	1.80E-27	-0.16	0.073	0.03

rs42044	7	92250140	G/T	0.034	0.002	9.90E-91	-0.054	0.057	0.343
rs4233765	2	19543250	C/A	-0.012	0.002	2.30E-10	-0.044	0.061	0.473
rs4252548	19	55879672	T/C	-0.051	0.005	6.60E-23	-0.159	0.159	0.319
rs4253755	22	46615376	A/G	0.018	0.002	7.10E-16	0.04	0.092	0.662
rs4259518	9	139322503	C/T	0.012	0.002	3.60E-15	-0.029	0.053	0.585
rs4287972	4	88645798	T/C	-0.02	0.001	1.10E-41	-0.034	0.05	0.495
rs4302125	18	22754860	C/T	-0.008	0.002	3.90E-08	-0.047	0.051	0.353
rs4307773	12	51144432	C/T	0.012	0.002	1.10E-14	0.028	0.051	0.587
rs4311660	8	23166656	A/C	-0.017	0.002	1.70E-23	0.033	0.056	0.561
rs4333914	10	23770658	A/G	0.012	0.002	3.10E-14	-0.012	0.056	0.823
rs4350272	10	25056118	G/A	-0.01	0.002	1.10E-09	0.012	0.059	0.845
rs4484960	1	45765523	T/C	0.012	0.002	5.20E-09	-0.034	0.067	0.615
rs4500751	16	15140211	T/C	-0.016	0.002	3.60E-23	-0.022	0.054	0.683
rs45446698	7	99332948	G/T	0.034	0.004	1.30E-19	-0.067	0.112	0.551
rs4558926	4	1748069	G/C	0.013	0.002	1.30E-18	0.006	0.054	0.905
rs4651157	1	183848761	T/G	0.01	0.002	1.80E-10	0.06	0.05	0.233
rs4659078	1	118877138	A/G	-0.012	0.002	6.90E-12	-0.049	0.059	0.408
rs4660457	1	41239793	G/A	-0.01	0.002	1.50E-08	0.013	0.06	0.829
rs4665972	2	27598097	C/T	0.017	0.002	6.10E-30	-0.033	0.052	0.52
rs4699384	4	100570681	A/T	0.018	0.002	2.10E-20	-0.131	0.081	0.108
rs4713941	6	36218219	G/C	-0.018	0.002	2.90E-23	0.056	0.057	0.323
rs4727453	7	77292821	G/A	0.009	0.002	1.40E-08	0.045	0.05	0.371
rs4735766	8	78099782	T/G	0.031	0.002	1.40E-75	-0.007	0.06	0.913
rs4737446	8	57665019	T/G	0.017	0.002	5.40E-26	0.021	0.053	0.689
rs4740628	9	15888333	G/A	0.012	0.002	1.80E-14	-0.054	0.05	0.282
rs4748012	10	12955138	A/G	0.009	0.002	1.80E-09	0.004	0.051	0.943
rs4792700	17	8166091	G/A	0.013	0.002	1.00E-10	0.054	0.08	0.506
rs4794006	17	47042117	A/G	-0.018	0.002	1.30E-33	0.086	0.05	0.088
rs4794907	17	30157176	C/G	-0.012	0.002	6.10E-09	0.034	0.07	0.628
rs4808736	19	18117488	A/T	-0.011	0.002	2.60E-10	-0.019	0.058	0.739
rs4833235	4	122695136	A/C	-0.012	0.002	2.70E-15	0.005	0.051	0.921
rs4865956	5	54882505	A/T	-0.019	0.002	3.30E-30	-0.055	0.056	0.325
rs4870056	6	152162227	A/G	0.021	0.001	1.10E-43	-0.076	0.051	0.133
rs4884094	13	79000742	C/G	-0.011	0.002	1.20E-09	-0.05	0.06	0.406
rs4905593	14	101146263	A/G	-0.017	0.002	2.30E-12	-0.003	0.075	0.972
rs491299	10	131750134	T/C	0.009	0.002	1.10E-09	0.07	0.055	0.201
rs4925137	17	17954535	G/A	-0.012	0.002	7.80E-09	0.002	0.063	0.978
rs4932430	15	89363866	C/A	0.023	0.002	7.70E-52	-0.004	0.051	0.937
rs4939837	18	46487998	G/A	-0.015	0.002	4.20E-22	0.048	0.052	0.354
rs4980067	10	81136129	A/C	-0.017	0.002	9.30E-30	0.038	0.051	0.455
rs500422	2	219432995	A/C	0.015	0.002	8.30E-24	-0.097	0.051	0.056
rs506154	7	28202079	C/T	-0.02	0.002	6.80E-35	0.028	0.053	0.595
rs519384	3	172168507	A/T	0.022	0.002	5.20E-40	0.062	0.056	0.269
rs524153	3	55525985	G/T	-0.01	0.001	1.60E-11	0.038	0.05	0.448
rs55749333	17	7371932	T/C	-0.023	0.002	1.40E-48	-0.014	0.05	0.779
rs558144	6	116724291	T/C	0.021	0.002	9.00E-32	-0.042	0.062	0.493
rs56247656	3	193742151	C/T	-0.008	0.002	4.60E-08	0.021	0.051	0.686
rs56288516	4	145196359	T/G	-0.019	0.002	1.50E-32	0.036	0.051	0.484
rs56397702	3	142304764	T/C	0.011	0.002	3.20E-08	0.125	0.066	0.06
rs57179316	3	67341110	T/C	-0.021	0.002	2.80E-17	-0.031	0.099	0.754
rs5745143	5	172582546	T/C	0.016	0.003	2.30E-09	0.052	0.139	0.71
rs5752989	22	30365780	A/G	-0.009	0.002	4.90E-09	0.01	0.05	0.85
rs58842569	20	4099558	G/T	0.01	0.002	2.70E-10	-0.09	0.054	0.098
rs58917892	22	46177446	A/T	-0.011	0.002	1.80E-08	-0.08	0.067	0.227
rs58945562	10	31111110	A/G	0.021	0.002	1.10E-19	-0.075	0.073	0.304
rs59643265	17	1630395	C/T	-0.01	0.002	2.00E-09	-0.047	0.057	0.408
rs59945160	16	4356206	G/C	0.023	0.002	2.70E-38	-0.025	0.056	0.661
rs59985551	2	56106928	T/C	-0.029	0.002	1.70E-59	-0.03	0.06	0.622
rs599892	1	39922884	G/C	0.01	0.002	2.70E-10	0.018	0.058	0.756
rs6026576	20	57459167	G/A	-0.013	0.002	3.10E-16	-0.046	0.053	0.381
rs6060983	20	30420924	C/T	0.017	0.002	3.60E-24	-0.063	0.051	0.222
rs60619356	9	4175945	C/T	-0.014	0.002	1.50E-09	0.004	0.095	0.97
rs6063678	20	50231518	G/A	-0.011	0.002	1.30E-11	0.037	0.054	0.495
rs606452	11	75276178	C/A	-0.025	0.002	2.80E-30	-0.006	0.065	0.921

rs6066104	20	45530530	T/C	0.017	0.002	4.20E-26	-0.073	0.052	0.162
rs60695939	2	218600462	C/T	-0.049	0.005	2.20E-25	0.167	0.164	0.309
rs6082358	20	21230455	T/C	-0.016	0.002	1.10E-22	0.003	0.056	0.953
rs608251	11	125979757	A/C	-0.011	0.002	8.00E-11	-0.036	0.055	0.511
rs6117293	20	6466644	A/G	-0.02	0.002	3.50E-38	-0.035	0.05	0.486
rs61196936	2	24830463	G/A	0.021	0.002	4.20E-33	-0.02	0.056	0.717
rs613813	13	22343925	C/T	0.009	0.002	2.50E-08	-0.097	0.053	0.068
rs61732778	3	187443314	A/G	0.03	0.003	3.40E-24	-0.065	0.091	0.474
rs61745017	1	203054651	A/G	-0.028	0.004	1.80E-10	-0.018	0.123	0.884
rs62027307	15	77303108	T/C	0.016	0.003	2.10E-08	0.085	0.08	0.293
rs62054823	17	43929029	G/A	-0.025	0.002	5.70E-44	-0.067	0.092	0.467
rs62102286	18	46592408	G/T	0.034	0.002	#####	-0.091	0.054	0.094
rs62172372	2	188242369	G/A	0.016	0.002	1.40E-16	0.035	0.059	0.549
rs62217511	21	40013566	C/T	0.011	0.002	2.10E-09	-0.026	0.058	0.658
rs623356	1	218647386	C/T	-0.016	0.002	3.80E-27	0.084	0.05	0.094
rs62372093	5	42884742	C/T	0.02	0.003	3.80E-13	-0.033	0.073	0.65
rs62390617	6	1623627	C/G	0.016	0.002	6.20E-13	0.054	0.092	0.558
rs62419228	6	83800898	A/G	0.013	0.002	1.20E-08	-0.005	0.068	0.942
rs62442203	7	28829253	C/G	-0.023	0.002	1.60E-49	-0.1	0.051	0.048
rs62515432	8	57123523	C/T	0.036	0.002	1.50E-84	-0.02	0.056	0.719
rs62621197	19	8670147	T/C	-0.071	0.004	2.30E-65	0.205	0.18	0.255
rs62621400	15	101718239	G/C	-0.051	0.003	1.20E-55	-0.032	0.106	0.764
rs631248	1	44071221	A/G	0.013	0.002	3.10E-12	0.049	0.062	0.432
rs6426786	1	23470460	T/C	-0.014	0.002	1.00E-19	0.009	0.052	0.856
rs6426798	1	19719728	T/C	0.016	0.002	2.00E-22	-0.082	0.054	0.129
rs6442266	3	11650010	A/G	0.028	0.004	1.00E-15	-0.104	0.113	0.356
rs6480947	10	81236210	G/A	0.019	0.002	2.50E-20	0.057	0.062	0.354
rs648103	3	27550301	C/T	-0.01	0.002	7.90E-11	0.045	0.053	0.399
rs6508712	19	37815381	G/T	-0.01	0.002	4.70E-10	-0.045	0.05	0.376
rs6574257	14	76383219	G/A	-0.012	0.002	1.50E-12	0.084	0.061	0.166
rs660745	19	49219459	C/T	-0.01	0.002	4.20E-11	0.034	0.051	0.5
rs6673081	1	154989595	C/T	-0.009	0.002	2.20E-09	-0.039	0.051	0.44
rs66746153	4	166322542	G/T	0.013	0.002	4.10E-16	-0.037	0.057	0.516
rs6675441	1	214659762	A/G	-0.013	0.002	6.40E-14	-0.05	0.067	0.457
rs66989638	2	106689736	A/G	0.019	0.002	8.80E-17	0.037	0.064	0.564
rs67026445	12	90156745	C/T	-0.011	0.002	1.70E-10	-0.003	0.053	0.962
rs6714546	2	33361425	G/A	0.02	0.002	2.20E-35	0.077	0.059	0.193
rs67150549	11	16529102	G/A	0.009	0.002	8.30E-09	-0.011	0.052	0.827
rs6728237	2	119045109	T/C	0.012	0.002	3.50E-15	-0.047	0.05	0.344
rs6753449	2	72160412	T/C	0.01	0.002	2.90E-10	-0.027	0.054	0.622
rs6754426	2	232322779	A/G	-0.015	0.002	4.80E-22	0.019	0.051	0.706
rs67631072	1	38461821	T/C	-0.017	0.002	5.50E-31	-0.05	0.052	0.338
rs6818581	4	146697063	G/A	0.041	0.007	2.40E-09	0.27	0.285	0.343
rs6824748	4	17997066	A/G	-0.046	0.002	#####	-0.03	0.085	0.721
rs6874142	5	172753555	G/T	0.024	0.002	1.90E-21	-0.025	0.088	0.773
rs6907253	6	158695244	G/C	0.018	0.002	4.30E-15	0.035	0.073	0.628
rs6909857	6	142701158	G/A	-0.053	0.002	#####	0.001	0.057	0.99
rs6923431	6	129824754	C/A	0.013	0.002	5.40E-15	0.007	0.053	0.902
rs6968039	7	120803463	A/G	0.01	0.001	9.00E-11	0.115	0.05	0.022
rs6977416	7	150542711	A/G	0.022	0.002	4.00E-44	0.051	0.052	0.332
rs700518	15	51529112	C/T	0.014	0.002	6.20E-20	0.061	0.05	0.221
rs7018405	8	25867198	C/G	-0.01	0.002	7.40E-10	-0.073	0.055	0.184
rs702883	2	65752085	G/A	0.013	0.002	1.40E-16	0.011	0.053	0.836
rs7035049	9	16413779	A/G	0.014	0.002	5.50E-20	-0.067	0.051	0.183
rs704660	11	30447998	T/C	0.016	0.002	5.40E-26	0.032	0.051	0.532
rs7071326	10	103434170	A/G	-0.011	0.002	4.80E-12	0.074	0.056	0.186
rs709284	12	122631752	C/T	0.014	0.002	4.60E-18	-0.032	0.051	0.528
rs71373506	17	42631469	C/G	-0.015	0.002	7.80E-11	0.089	0.064	0.163
rs7148567	14	103882234	T/C	-0.009	0.002	3.50E-08	-0.073	0.053	0.172
rs7148741	14	21892165	A/G	-0.017	0.002	5.00E-22	0.01	0.057	0.856
rs7155279	14	92485881	T/G	-0.012	0.002	5.70E-14	0.082	0.054	0.128
rs7162063	15	89223930	G/A	0.009	0.002	5.00E-09	0.056	0.059	0.337
rs7165983	15	94509415	G/A	0.011	0.002	2.00E-13	-0.02	0.051	0.69
rs7193833	16	73220771	C/T	0.011	0.002	8.10E-11	-0.028	0.053	0.6

rs7221208	17	69317890	A/G	0.017	0.002	3.70E-27	0.057	0.051	0.266
rs7223535	17	29211667	A/G	-0.018	0.002	1.60E-26	-0.036	0.056	0.518
rs723149	7	46577056	G/A	-0.017	0.002	5.30E-28	-0.016	0.05	0.75
rs7239515	18	41462359	C/G	0.013	0.002	1.30E-15	-0.004	0.052	0.945
rs7252363	19	46354793	A/G	-0.012	0.002	3.70E-14	0.001	0.057	0.993
rs72634327	17	79072011	G/A	-0.011	0.002	1.20E-09	0.011	0.064	0.863
rs72674269	1	63635659	T/A	-0.015	0.003	4.40E-09	0.001	0.088	0.988
rs72693398	8	145002536	A/G	-0.017	0.002	1.20E-27	-0.006	0.051	0.909
rs72814356	2	60024056	G/C	-0.009	0.002	4.30E-08	0.089	0.053	0.097
rs72826838	17	42722530	G/A	0.017	0.002	2.00E-19	-0.045	0.071	0.529
rs72876043	18	11172619	A/G	0.011	0.002	4.90E-09	0.077	0.072	0.282
rs7306710	12	66376091	C/T	-0.029	0.002	1.40E-82	-0.012	0.05	0.81
rs73112429	3	4749245	T/C	0.012	0.002	8.70E-09	0.05	0.075	0.504
rs73125628	20	20066701	T/C	-0.013	0.002	3.60E-14	0.027	0.052	0.611
rs73173142	13	41113186	A/C	-0.021	0.003	1.00E-09	0.091	0.134	0.499
rs73189390	21	17383170	A/G	-0.013	0.002	8.10E-12	0.046	0.063	0.469
rs73215668	4	12869917	C/T	-0.023	0.003	5.90E-19	0.004	0.109	0.969
rs734586	2	241734754	C/T	0.012	0.002	7.50E-16	-0.031	0.051	0.538
rs74318446	19	42535234	G/A	-0.018	0.002	1.80E-14	0.017	0.095	0.856
rs743283	8	37336397	A/G	0.01	0.002	2.10E-08	0.036	0.062	0.565
rs74431741	12	4033760	A/G	0.039	0.004	2.80E-28	0.098	0.179	0.585
rs74751480	3	32966644	A/G	-0.037	0.005	1.40E-13	0.015	0.185	0.934
rs747680	20	61507075	C/T	0.011	0.002	7.00E-13	0.004	0.05	0.941
rs7491366	13	47928776	C/T	0.01	0.002	1.20E-09	0.063	0.053	0.233
rs7523079	1	19962874	C/T	-0.013	0.002	4.50E-13	-0.026	0.061	0.666
rs75495843	3	38051211	A/G	0.057	0.004	9.50E-39	-0.186	0.161	0.247
rs7558918	2	23997661	G/T	0.03	0.002	5.10E-89	-0.002	0.05	0.963
rs7565457	2	111935478	T/C	0.01	0.001	8.90E-11	0.059	0.05	0.242
rs75884468	12	46605282	A/G	-0.025	0.005	3.60E-08	-0.001	0.137	0.993
rs762025	2	32603805	A/G	-0.015	0.002	9.50E-22	0.014	0.053	0.798
rs7627561	3	188179909	T/C	-0.01	0.002	3.80E-10	0.034	0.051	0.496
rs763665	16	72078043	T/C	-0.014	0.002	1.30E-11	0.007	0.067	0.914
rs7645611	3	53125297	C/G	0.025	0.002	4.20E-24	0.209	0.1	0.036
rs7656545	4	95569216	T/A	0.01	0.002	1.40E-08	-0.058	0.069	0.394
rs766406	6	26319588	T/G	-0.018	0.002	7.00E-32	0.046	0.055	0.404
rs76750172	13	28395297	T/C	0.028	0.005	1.00E-08	0.057	0.151	0.706
rs76763327	9	12443459	G/C	-0.022	0.003	4.10E-11	-0.048	0.111	0.662
rs768023	6	108876002	A/G	0.017	0.002	1.60E-27	-0.009	0.051	0.858
rs7681267	4	87073599	C/T	0.043	0.006	3.70E-13	0.06	0.505	0.905
rs76813126	4	109407803	T/C	0.01	0.002	2.30E-09	-0.005	0.067	0.945
rs76895963	12	4384844	G/T	0.113	0.006	6.20E-84	-0.334	0.149	0.025
rs76946649	12	20681638	C/G	0.028	0.004	4.60E-16	0.102	0.118	0.388
rs7733195	5	172994624	A/G	-0.025	0.002	6.10E-57	0.05	0.051	0.33
rs7751170	6	140160072	T/C	0.012	0.002	1.10E-10	-0.153	0.062	0.014
rs7753558	6	117523471	A/C	0.026	0.002	1.60E-64	0.114	0.054	0.035
rs7755185	6	152339615	G/A	0.017	0.002	2.70E-25	0.009	0.052	0.867
rs77556405	17	46463909	A/G	-0.016	0.002	1.60E-15	-0.091	0.061	0.135
rs77735628	2	68378367	A/C	-0.027	0.003	1.30E-22	0.014	0.102	0.891
rs78092448	2	12162651	G/A	0.014	0.002	3.00E-09	-0.029	0.084	0.729
rs7811889	7	56140357	G/A	0.01	0.002	6.70E-09	-0.095	0.062	0.127
rs7814941	8	130718859	G/A	-0.039	0.002	1.20E-98	0.115	0.066	0.081
rs78198962	2	233094868	T/C	0.052	0.004	8.10E-35	-0.2	0.193	0.299
rs7822301	8	13273425	G/T	0.011	0.002	1.90E-13	-0.007	0.05	0.888
rs7842234	8	96430516	G/C	-0.018	0.002	4.60E-19	0.085	0.075	0.262
rs78487224	18	19133687	A/G	-0.018	0.002	5.60E-13	-0.125	0.073	0.084
rs7869176	9	85022933	G/A	0.016	0.002	6.70E-19	0.013	0.06	0.833
rs78760367	7	5392630	A/G	-0.014	0.002	1.30E-09	-0.077	0.085	0.367
rs78818340	15	61591076	A/G	0.019	0.003	3.30E-09	0.078	0.113	0.489
rs79040955	11	95867902	T/C	0.013	0.002	1.80E-09	-0.028	0.072	0.703
rs7926837	11	15708792	A/G	-0.011	0.002	3.10E-09	0.04	0.054	0.462
rs7927966	11	58376276	T/C	0.012	0.002	3.30E-11	-0.011	0.057	0.844
rs7960147	12	46751454	T/C	0.02	0.002	2.70E-40	0.001	0.052	0.988
rs7972283	12	94255142	G/T	-0.015	0.002	1.20E-24	-0.012	0.051	0.813
rs79728014	11	46062245	G/A	0.015	0.002	3.50E-12	-0.04	0.072	0.573

rs79747671	12	103140344	T/C	-0.033	0.002	6.10E-43	0.013	0.075	0.865
rs798490	7	2801542	A/G	-0.04	0.002	#####	0.049	0.052	0.345
rs7994573	13	115008388	C/T	-0.019	0.002	4.20E-27	0.055	0.059	0.352
rs80024170	3	56669359	C/T	-0.02	0.003	2.10E-15	-0.084	0.079	0.29
rs8016583	14	53067681	A/G	0.009	0.002	2.50E-08	-0.003	0.05	0.96
rs80322448	9	100781146	A/G	-0.019	0.003	5.30E-12	-0.143	0.098	0.142
rs8042740	15	48686310	T/C	-0.024	0.003	1.80E-19	-0.046	0.076	0.543
rs8096254	18	20713215	A/G	0.021	0.002	6.60E-33	0.019	0.056	0.736
rs8103992	19	19665643	C/A	-0.017	0.002	3.20E-20	0.144	0.082	0.078
rs822530	7	148631555	T/A	0.025	0.002	1.60E-40	-0.084	0.067	0.212
rs823118	1	205723572	T/C	-0.018	0.001	9.10E-34	-0.127	0.051	0.013
rs839239	3	58002885	T/C	-0.02	0.002	2.80E-35	0.07	0.053	0.186
rs852927	6	72181137	T/C	0.013	0.002	7.20E-18	-0.028	0.053	0.596
rs858528	17	7574936	T/C	-0.017	0.002	1.50E-13	-0.003	0.081	0.974
rs867529	2	88913273	C/G	0.02	0.002	9.60E-34	0.005	0.053	0.928
rs870713	9	84227158	A/C	-0.014	0.002	8.00E-21	0.073	0.051	0.156
rs875908	14	23907608	G/C	0.01	0.002	3.50E-10	-0.072	0.053	0.169
rs878749	9	35812623	T/G	0.011	0.002	7.50E-09	0.139	0.07	0.047
rs881926	7	38029785	T/G	-0.015	0.002	5.80E-13	0.022	0.07	0.757
rs884205	18	60054857	C/A	0.013	0.002	1.20E-13	0.047	0.056	0.398
rs900400	3	156798775	C/T	0.013	0.002	2.90E-18	0.044	0.054	0.412
rs912999	20	54836630	A/T	-0.011	0.002	4.80E-12	0.04	0.055	0.468
rs917305	16	4440593	T/C	0.013	0.002	9.00E-13	0.032	0.059	0.584
rs919353	5	68056719	A/G	-0.009	0.002	1.60E-09	0.014	0.051	0.782
rs9270576	6	32561068	T/C	0.013	0.002	1.80E-14	0.075	0.057	0.188
rs931550	12	65861284	G/A	0.012	0.002	3.10E-16	-0.07	0.05	0.166
rs9318373	13	76363721	A/G	-0.009	0.002	1.90E-08	-0.07	0.052	0.18
rs9327336	5	123990270	C/T	0.01	0.002	6.80E-11	0.002	0.051	0.976
rs932988	9	132218356	C/T	-0.012	0.001	2.40E-15	-0.025	0.051	0.629
rs933717	16	87415250	C/T	-0.009	0.002	1.70E-09	0.055	0.05	0.271
rs9344126	6	81907559	C/T	-0.023	0.002	7.10E-53	-0.029	0.051	0.569
rs935728	14	80957923	T/C	0.01	0.002	2.20E-10	-0.052	0.053	0.322
rs9357471	6	45090977	T/C	0.023	0.002	2.10E-52	-0.001	0.051	0.984
rs9379084	6	7231843	A/G	-0.036	0.002	5.00E-51	-0.026	0.08	0.747
rs9391254	6	105377347	T/C	0.014	0.002	2.10E-17	0.028	0.054	0.608
rs9399365	6	141729498	A/T	-0.011	0.002	6.50E-11	0.033	0.057	0.56
rs9409429	9	94337510	T/C	0.014	0.002	6.70E-14	-0.071	0.064	0.265
rs9435731	1	17306029	A/C	0.022	0.001	1.50E-47	0.008	0.05	0.871
rs9459598	6	166577701	T/G	-0.019	0.001	4.40E-36	0.048	0.051	0.352
rs946602	1	9340695	C/T	0.013	0.002	2.90E-17	0.035	0.056	0.528
rs9492799	6	131381281	A/G	0.016	0.002	1.00E-15	0.058	0.071	0.415
rs949302	18	3264155	C/G	0.01	0.002	1.30E-08	-0.108	0.052	0.039
rs9502498	6	6763446	T/C	-0.01	0.002	2.60E-10	0.012	0.059	0.835
rs9568031	13	48897520	T/C	-0.011	0.002	1.30E-10	0.004	0.054	0.942
rs9601323	13	80700397	A/G	0.01	0.002	6.70E-12	0.03	0.05	0.549
rs968427	8	41165794	C/T	-0.01	0.002	1.30E-11	0.107	0.05	0.035
rs9739070	12	123771032	G/A	-0.034	0.002	7.20E-74	0.055	0.062	0.372
rs9745989	16	49888931	C/T	0.014	0.002	5.30E-19	0.053	0.055	0.336
rs9778087	1	941539	T/C	0.009	0.002	1.30E-09	-0.145	0.051	0.005
rs9784530	4	73527617	T/C	0.011	0.002	3.10E-12	-0.063	0.05	0.207
rs9788982	17	68139785	G/A	-0.018	0.002	2.40E-15	-0.056	0.08	0.485
rs9809116	3	72397279	G/A	-0.017	0.002	1.00E-29	0.035	0.053	0.509
rs9861	12	672372	A/G	0.011	0.002	6.00E-13	-0.042	0.051	0.416
rs989235	5	67193520	G/C	0.015	0.002	1.00E-12	-0.071	0.085	0.402
rs9925261	16	72927533	C/A	0.011	0.002	1.20E-11	-0.006	0.054	0.917
rs9988728	10	53289428	A/G	0.012	0.002	1.40E-12	-0.026	0.058	0.654